

BACTERIAL TRANSMISSION OF STAPHYLOCOCCAL INFECTION AMONG BLOOD DONORS BASED ON GENERAL INTERNATIONAL STATISTICS

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Introduction: The problem of blood-borne infections is one of the important problems of modern transfusiology. According to WHO recommendations, the use of blood from donors who have not been tested for infections is prohibited. Blood-borne infections include infections of the staphylococcus group (Ottomar Ernst Felix Rosenbach, born in 1884). Modern laboratory technologies for the diagnosis of infectious pathology, based on immunochemical research methods, make it possible to assess the presence and level of specific antibodies, which makes it possible to predict the course of the infectious process and the epidemic, its dynamics, assessment and consequences (Adieva A.A. et al., 2009; Roberts S. et al., 2011).

Key words: bacteriocarriage, antibiotic resistance, staphylococcus, types of staphylococcus, ways of transmission of staphylococcus, immune plazma.

Purpose: To study the serological prevalence of staphylococcal infections among the donor population in blood transfusion centers.

Materials and methods: Within the framework of this study, *Staphylococcus aureus* can normally live for years on the skin and mucous membranes, in the human intestine, without causing harm. Thus, the bacterium constantly lives in the nasopharynx in about 20% of people, occasionally in 60%. The blood serum was analyzed for IgM antibodies (immunoglobulin G) to staphylococcal pathogens using a commercially available kit for ELISA (manufacturer: 000 NPO Diagnostic Systems, Nizhny Novgorod) in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. There were 2 groups of healthy young people aged 20 to 30 years under observation:

116 people – students of the II-III courses of Medical institutes, those who practically do not attend the clinic (group I) and interns – 125 people (group II) working in a therapeutic clinic. The results were qualitatively expressed as positive and negative. In the process of further studying the spread of staphylococcal infection, it is planned to cover even more groups of donors of different ages and professions as goals and objectives, this will amount to at least 2 large different groups of donors (1000 donors with identified antistaphylococcal antibodies and 50 immune donors). 2 control groups were also examined to determine if the results were correct. It was found that the sensitivity of the test is 100%, and the specificity is 99.6%.

Results: As follows from the presented materials, various types of staphylococci in the nasal cavity were detected in all examined patients, the frequency of infection of the throat cavity by students and doctors was not statistically significant and amounted to 59.5 and 53.6%, respectively

Conclusion: Sometimes donating blood can save someone's life. People with herpes can also become donors, but only during remission. After all, when the virus is active, it can affect the health of the patient who is being transfused with donated blood. This is fraught with pathological processes in the brain, liver, and can also cause allergic reactions and diseases of the visual organs. However, during remission, the virus is not dangerous. During a quiet period, the virus is localized in nerve cells, it is not in the blood, so there are no obstacles to donation. To summarize, we can say the following: in addition to ensuring the safety of transfused blood, we also contribute to the study of the prevalence of staphylococcal infection among various population groups, having received the results of the study, we can subsequently improve the production of anti-staphylococcal serum, while minimizing both material costs and the cost of treatment. and it reduces the time to obtain ready-made anti-staphylococcal serum.

List of literature:

1.Электронная библиотека ДВГМУ :: МЕТИЦИЛЛИНРЕЗИСТЕНТНЫЕ ЗОЛОТИСТЫЕ СТАФИЛОКОККИ: ПРОБЛЕМА РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ В МИРЕ И РОССИИ. www.fesmu.ru. Дата обращения: 3 октября 2016.

2.Поспелова С.В., Горовиц Э.С., Еще раз о бактерионосительстве стафилококков Медицинский альманах № 2 (7) июнь 2009, стр.76

4. Реброва О.Ю. Статистический анализ медицинских данных. Москва, 2006. 276 с.

5. Сокова С. А. и др. Мониторинг носительства золотистого стафилококка среди лиц, обследованных с профилактической целью за 2009-2013 годы //Клиническая и профилактическая медицина: опыт и новые открытия. – 2014. – С. 155-158.

6.Ягофаров Ф. Ф. Лабораторная диагностика стафилококковой сенсбилизации //Medicine. – 2015. – №. 1. – С. 96.

7. Pospelova S.V., Horowitz E.S., Once again about the bacterial carrier of staphylococci Medical Almanac No. 2 (7) June 2009, p.76

8. Atlas of Medical microbiology, virology and immunology / Edited by A. A. Vorobyov, A. S. Bykov. — M.: Medical Information Agency, 2003.

The Internet:

<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

<https://amclinic.ru/med-spravochnik/stafilokokk>